

Delay Prediction in Supply Chains:

A Hybrid Graph-Based and Machine Learning Approach

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Master degree

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The slide features a dark green background with a lighter green circular graphic on the right side. The text is centered and reads "M4ESTRO Project Overview".

M4ESTRO Project Overview

Motivation & Purpose

Motivation

Global disruptions (pandemics, conflicts, climate events) expose the fragility of **manufacturers' supply chains**.

Resilience and **adaptability** are now essential to ensure continuity and competitiveness.

m4estro

Project

M4ESTRO is a European project uniting **18 partners** from 8 countries, including industrial pilots, technology providers and research institutions.

Launched on 1 December 2023, **duration of 42 months**.

Goals

Develop a resilient, transparent, and adaptive ecosystem under the **Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS)** paradigm, enhancing supply chain flexibility and robustness.

Industrial **Manufacturing As a Service STR**ategies and models for flexible, resilient, and re-configurable value networks through **Trusted and Transparent Operations**.

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Key Contributions

Supply Chain Modeling

Mathematical framework for modeling a single-manufacturer **supply chain**.

Indicators Design

Indicators to quantify:

- **Dispatch** and **shipment process durations**.
 - **Real-time traffic** and **weather** impacts on shipments.
 - Effect of **national holidays** on dispatch processes.
-

Prototype

Development of a **prototype** using pilot partner data and **deployment** on AWS cloud infrastructure.

Disruption indicators: monitor operations, detect real-time anomalies, measure impacts and enable rapid responses.

Task 1.2: design **indicators to detect internal disruptions**, within a **single-manufacturer supply chain**.

Dataset & External Sources

Pilot and Tracking Data

Pilot Order Data

FAE Technology, core dataset provider: *one-hundred order records* with supplier locations, timestamps and tracking links.

Carrier Tracking Data

17Track API to retrieve *shipment events* across multiple carriers, including *location, timestamp, and status*.

Geographical Data

Geonames API to standardize shipment events and supplier locations at a *city level*.

Three sources forming the **core dataset**, providing the foundational data that captures the **supply chain structure**.

Traffic, Weather and Holiday Data

Traffic Data

TomTom API to retrieve *road traffic* data, comparing ideal vs real-time conditions between two locations.

Weather Data

visualcrossing

Visual Crossing API to retrieve *weather* data, providing real-time conditions for any location.

Holiday Data

CALENDARIFIC

Calendarific API to retrieve *national holidays* worldwide, providing indications on supplier closures.

Three **complementary sources** enrich the core dataset, providing a **complete representation** of the supply chain.

Supply Chain Modeling

Supply Chain Graph Model

Graph Structure

Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG)

Vertices partitioned into:

- Supplier sites (sources).
- Intermediate facilities.
- Manufacturer (sink).

$$V = S \cup I \cup \{m\}$$

Shipments Flow

Flow function indicating the number of shipments transited through a given edge.

$$f: A \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$$

Flow conservation on intermediates vertices guarantees no loss or duplication in shipments.

$$\sum_{(i,v) \in A} f(i,v) = \sum_{(v,i) \in A} f(v,i), \quad \forall i \in I$$

Markov Chain Routing Model

Empirical Probabilities

Shipment flow used to estimate **empirical probabilities** of transition:

$$P_{vu} = \frac{f(v, u)}{\sum_{(v, z) \in A} f(v, z)}$$

Probabilistic Routing

Markov Property used to compute path probabilities:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{P}(\pi) &= \mathbb{P}(X_0 = v_0, X_1 = v_1, \dots, X_k = m) \\ &= \mathbb{P}(X_0 = v_0) \cdot \prod_{i=0}^{k-1} P_{v_i v_{i+1}} \end{aligned}$$

Carrier-Conditioned Dynamics

Shipment flows **conditioned** on the specific **carrier** to model distinct routing behaviors:

$$f^c(v, u) = \text{number of shipments from } v \text{ to } u \text{ executed by carrier } c$$

Shipments are represented as **maximal paths** ending in the manufacturer. The **routing process** is modeled using **discrete-time Markov chains**, capturing shipment trajectories as **stochastic processes** based on **empirical transition probabilities** derived from **historical shipment flows**.

Paths Extraction and Probability Distributions

Paths Extraction Methodology

Modified **Depth-First Search (DFS)** collects all shipment paths from a vertex v to the manufacturer m .

Dataset shows only a limited number of paths per vertex: **average 4 paths per vertex, maximum 24.**

Probability Distribution Computation

Given the collection of all the **maximal paths** for a vertex $v \in V$:

$$\Pi(v) = \{\pi_1, \pi_2, \dots, \pi_\ell\}$$

The associated **paths probabilities** conditioned by carrier c :

$$\mathbf{p}^c = (p_1^c, p_2^c, \dots, p_\ell^c)$$

Form a valid **probability distribution**.

For each vertex, **carrier behavior** is modeled by considering **all possible paths** to the manufacturer, along with the **probability** that each path is followed.

Historical Indicators

Definition

Time Probability Distributions

Dispatch times: a probability distribution for each supplier.

$$DT: S \rightarrow \mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}_+)$$

Shipment times: a probability distribution for each supplier–carrier pair.

$$ST: S \times C \rightarrow \mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}_+)$$

Statistical Metrics

Pointwise: expected value of the distribution.

$$DT_\mu(s) = \mathbb{E}[DT(s)], \quad \forall s \in S$$

Interval-based: β -level confidence interval of the distribution.

$$DT_\beta(s) = [L_\beta(s), U_\beta(s)]$$

$$\mathbb{P}(L_\beta(s) \leq X \leq U_\beta(s)) \geq \beta, \quad X \sim DT(s)$$

Historical indicators are statistical measures that characterize key **operational times** in the order fulfillment process, based exclusively on **historical data**.

Implementation

Theoretical Distribution

Gamma distributions chosen for their established use in supply-chain literature.

Parameter estimation via **Maximum Likelihood Estimation**.

Fitting Procedure

Outlier removal: Interquartile Range (IQR) method.

Goodness-of-fit checks: Q–Q plots and histograms.

Statistical validation: Kolmogorov–Smirnov tests show no evidence against the Gamma assumption.

Realtime Indicators

Overview

Realtime Indicators Hierarchy

Granularity	Scope
Vertex	Supplier and carrier facility.
Route	Carrier route between two locations.
Path	Supplier to manufacturer carrier path.
Graph	Overall supply chain network.

Realtime indicators are statistical measures that provide actionable insights into the current state of the **supply chain**, combining:

- Historical indicators.
- Supply chain graph.
- Real-time data.

Definition (1)

Vertex Level

Estimated Dispatch Time (EDT_{μ}): Scalar

- Based on the **DT historical indicator**.
- Includes **national holidays** to estimate the dispatch time of a supplier site.

Vertex Time (VT_{β}): Interval

- Based on the **historical processing time distribution** of a carrier facility.
- Provides a **β -level confidence interval** of the facility processing time.

Route Level

Traffic & Weather Meta Index (TMI, WMI) Scalar

- Based on **real-time data** retrieved from external services.
- Provide a measurement of **traffic** and **weather impacts** on carrier routes.

Route Time (RT_{β}): Interval

- Based on the **historical travel time distribution** of carrier routes.
- Provides a **β -level confidence interval** of the route travel time.

Definition (2)

Path Level

Path Time (PT_{β}): Interval

- Based on VT_{β} and RT_{β} **realtime indicators**.
- Aggregates **vertex** and **route time intervals** along a **path** to estimate the shipment's **remaining duration**.

Transit Time (TT_{β}): Interval

- Based on the **ST** historical indicator.
- Provides a β -level **confidence interval** of the shipment's **remaining duration**.

$$TT_{\beta}(s, c) = \max(ST_{\beta}(s, c) - t, 0)$$

Graph Level

Expected Path Time ($E - PT_{\beta}$): Interval

- Combines the PT_{β} estimations over **all the possible paths** from a vertex to the manufacturer according to their likelihood.

$$E - PT_{\beta} = \sum_{i=1}^{\ell} p_i^c \cdot PT_{\beta}(\pi_i)$$

Total Forecasted Shipment Time (TFST): Interval

- **Convex combination** of TT_{β} and $E - PT_{\beta}$.

$$TFST = \alpha \cdot TT_{\beta_1} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot E - PT_{\beta_2}$$

Implementation (1)

Objective

Transit Time (TT): effective for on-time shipments; unable to manage advances or delays.

Path Time (PT): high uncertainty at the start; able to handle advances and delays.

Early phase: prioritize **Transit Time** to manage higher uncertainty and limited timing deviations.

Progressing phase: prioritize **Path Time** as uncertainty decreases and timing deviations emerge.

Solution

Implement α as a **non-increasing function** of the **proportion of expected shipment time** that has **elapsed**:

$$\tau = \frac{t}{ST_{\mu}(s, c)}$$

Three proposed implementations:

1. **Constant:** $\alpha = k$
2. **Linear:** $\alpha(\tau) = \max(1 - \tau, 0)$
3. **Polynomial:** $\alpha(\tau; \langle TT \rangle) = (1 - \tau)^q$, $q = \frac{1}{\langle TT \rangle} - 1$

$$TFST = \alpha \cdot TT + (1 - \alpha) \cdot PT$$

Implementation (2)

$$\alpha(\tau) = \max(1 - \tau, 0)$$

Prioritize PT over TT as shipment time progresses.

$$\alpha(\tau; \langle TT \rangle) = (1 - \tau)^q, \quad q = \frac{1}{\langle TT \rangle} - 1$$

Tune $\langle TT \rangle$ to minimize the total estimation error of TFST relative to the observed shipment times.

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Protoype & Experimental Evaluation

Prototype Architecture

Implementation & Deployment

Developed in **Python** with deployment on **AWS**:

- **Lambda Functions & Layers.**
- **RDS (Relational Database Service).**
- **S3 (Object Storage).**
- **API Gateway.**
- **SQS (Simple Queue Service).**

Modularity & Configurability

Dynamic hyperparameter tuning via centralized configuration table.

Modular design enabling independent evolution of individual components.

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Evaluation Methodology

Time Resolution

Distributions fitted using **hourly-resolution** data.

System **evaluated** at **daily scale** using two approaches:

- **Hourly-based:** metrics computed from hourly predictions, then reported by day.
- **Daily-based:** predictions discretized into business days, with metrics directly evaluated at this scale.

Evaluation steps

1. Quantitative evaluation on:
 - **Sharpness:** width of predicted intervals.
 - **Coverage:** proportion of observations within the predicted interval.
 - **Interval Score:** single measure accounting for both sharpness and coverage.
2. **Sensitivity Analysis:** assessing model coverage across varying confidence levels.
3. **Visualization** of the evolution of **shipment estimates**.

Evaluation focused on the system's ability to accurately predict **delivery time windows** for orders, leveraging **event data** reported by **carriers** throughout the shipment process.

Quantitative Evaluation

Operational Stage	Sharpness (days)		Coverage (%)		Interval Score (days)	
	Hourly	Daily	Hourly	Daily	Hourly	Daily
Dispatch	2.15	2.20	0.28	0.56	4.22	4.26
Shipment	1.03	1.18	0.52	0.84	1.45	1.63

Training Set – 90% Confidence

Operational Stage	Sharpness (days)		Coverage (%)		Interval Score (days)	
	Hourly	Daily	Hourly	Daily	Hourly	Daily
Dispatch	2.87	3.00	0.3	0.5	7.81	7.44
Shipment	1.30	1.55	0.63	0.86	1.99	2.20

Test Set – 90% Confidence

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Sensitivity Analysis

Evaluation

Coverage assessed on the test set across multiple nominal confidence levels.

Hour-resolution estimates show **under-reliability**.

Day-resolution estimates show **over-reliability** up to a nominal confidence of 0.85

Evolution of Shipment Estimates (1)

Evolution of Time Estimates across Order Steps - Order 12

Evolution of Shipment Estimates (2)

Evolution of Time Estimates across Order Steps - Order 20

Evolution of Shipment Estimates (3)

Evolution of Time Estimates across Order Steps - Order 54

Evolution of Shipment Estimates (4)

Evolution of Time Estimates across Order Steps - Order 93

Evolution of Shipment Estimates (5)

Evolution of Time Estimates across Order Steps - Order 96

Conclusion

Future Developments

Data Expansion

Expand the **dataset** and refine all data-driven components to improve **calibration**, enhance indicators and increase **reliability** of predictions.

Refinement of Indicators Implementation

Implement and validate more advanced **solutions** for specific **indicators**.

Multi-Manufacturer Extension

Extend framework to support **multiple manufacturers** and more complex operational contexts.

Future development should focus on acquiring more **data** to **improve calibration** and support the implementation of more sophisticated solutions for specific **indicators**.

References

L. R. Ford and D. R. Fulkerson, “Maximal flow through a network,” Canadian Journal of Mathematics, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 399–404, 1956.

J. R. Norris, Markov Chains. Cambridge University Press, 1998.

G. Grimmett and D. Stirzaker, Probability and Random Processes, 3rd. Oxford University Press, 2001.

A. V. Hill, J. M. Hays, and E. Naveh, “A model for optimal delivery time guarantees,” Journal of service research, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 254–264, 2000

T. Gneiting and A. E. Raftery, “Strictly proper scoring rules, prediction and estimation,” Journal of the American Statistical Association, vol. 102, no. 477, pp. 359–378, 2007.

Y. Huang, A. Bárdossy, and K. Zhang, “Sensitivity of hydrological models to temporal and spatial resolutions of rainfall data,” Hydrology and Earth System Sciences, vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 2647–2663, 2019.

